

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE USE OF THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE OF EASTERN SCIENTISTS IN THE ORIENTATION OF STUDENTS TO THE PROFESSION

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Abstract. *In the text of the article, the student should be able to represent and evaluate their own capabilities, possess information about the possibilities of various professions. Information is given on the socio-economic, spiritual, ethical, pedagogical and psychological aspects of education, the role of parents, school, independent choice of life and work path young generation in choosing a profession. The pedagogical principles of using the spiritual heritage of Eastern scientists in the professional orientation of students are also covered in detail.*

Keywords: *profession, knowledge, upbringing, choice of profession, teacher, school, intellect, educational and methodical literature, recommendations, developments, instructions, training, spiritual heritage, material value.*

Today, the ever-expanding world of professions, the acceleration of scientific and technical progress to date have made the long-standing issue of choosing a profession in student youth a serious problem. Therefore, it is appropriate that the choice of profession is interpreted not only at the level of a problem of personal, but also social significance of a person taken separately. A number of decisions, decrees are being signed and implemented on the work of directing students to the profession in the building of the reforms of our country. Our country President stressed the need for young people in the event, various meetings, lectures held during their visit to each region, as well as in the depths of their reforms to acquire professional skills that contribute to the future of our country.

As noted by our president: “if we do not properly educate our children, if we do not every minute every day be aware of their behavior, their mood, if we do not teach them science and trade, if we do not find a suitable job, it is not at all a question to miss this deposit.”

Of course, parents, teachers and school psychologists are of great importance in the choice of professions in our country, depending on the available abilities of students in them.

As a result of our Talk, great attention is paid to the orientation of student youth to the profession in our country. In particular, during our visit to Fergana in 2020, our president gave instructions to the Ministry of public education on the topic. The president specifically touched on the issues of employment of young people, their orientation to the profession, noting that from the new school year from the 7th grade, students should be directed to the profession. The process of vocational guidance should be viewed as a scientific practical system of independent and free selection of the profession of students based on their individual characteristics. As you know, a student should have the skills to be able to imagine and assess his capabilities in choosing a profession, information about the capabilities of various professions. In this regard, a number of other decisions were made by the head of our country.

In our country, from time immemorial, our Eastern Allies expressed their opinion on the profession in their works. In particular, Abu Nasr Farabi also calls on people to work honestly and

acquire a profession. Farobi believes that man is not an "impotent servant", but a Supreme maturation," a being with the brilliance of reason, capable of creating everything he needs". Another of our allomas is the Sultan of the word estate Alisher Navoi, who in his time turned to young people and wrote that if you want to sunbathe, then mature your profession. An example is the spiritual heritage of Eastern thinkers, equal to duru-gavhari, in the first goal of educating our youth to teach them a profession. J. Avesto, the 11th-century "Kabusnoma" by Kaykows, Abu Nasr Forabi's "pursuit of happiness", the "commentary of the faithful", "Kalila and Dimna" by the Indian philosopher Beidabo (Bedpoy), Al-Khwarazmi's "O'gites", Abu Rayhon Beruni's "minerology", Yusuf Khos Khojib's "Qutadg bilig", Mahmud Qoshi's "Devonu-lexicotit turk", Ahmad Yugnaki's "Hibat-ul Haqayiq", Examples include the "Ruboi" of Pahlavan Mahmud, the "Hadiths" collected by Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Ismail al-Bukhari, Lutfi's "Flower and Navruz", Alisher Nawai's "Khamsa", "Mahbub-ul-qulub", Aruz Samarqandi's "rare stories", Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's "Boburnoma", and many other examples of literary, historical, cultural and educational heritage. Abu Rayhon Beruni was one of the first in human history to suggest that children should be taught to work from an early age, to raise adult labor to be oppressive, and to teach a child to science and the profession should be the focus of the family. Alloma singled out the fact that the Labor Education started in the family should be continued in connection with education at school and teaching a trade. The great thinker carefully studied the inheritance from generation to generation on the basis of Labor and professional succession and highly appreciated the craft activities of people. In itself, it is clear that the surreal activity laid the groundwork for the widespread use of ingenuity among artisan Masters in the form of demanding complex labor, deep knowledge. Sahibqiron Amir Temur attached great importance to the further development of crafts – textiles, wood and stone carving, carpet weaving, pottery, metalworking, and agriculture, livestock and trade, which were separated into an independent sphere on the basis of a large division of labor in his kingdom. Therefore, there was an opportunity for the emergence of new professions in social life, the path to mass unemployment was not laid.

Our ancestors in their works have given a huge emphasis to the professional labor education and upbringing of young people. They approached vocational education as a necessary component of training and education, and believed that it was necessary to carry it together with mental, physical and moral education. Given their abilities and inclinations to young people, one can seriously consider and admonitions about the choice of the type of Labor. It is advisable to make the most effective use of test, questionnaire, interview methods as well as psychological methodologies in matters of professional orientation – carried out on this topic. Yana also has durga's equal opinions on various professions in the works, meditations, guides of Ahmad Donish, Amir Temur, Abdurahman Jami and others.

Having gained fame in the 19th century for his thought on education, ethics, sophistication, Ahmad Donish gives a number of reflections on the teaching profession.

As we look at Ahmad wise's views on Career Choice, career orientation professional people, we see that in his views on the teaching profession, he paid great attention to the issue of morality. He sees the teacher as a strong influence on the students. He argues that it is harmful in ideology for those who choose a teaching profession to have an intention of impurity because they spread moral perversion among the younger generation. Hence, Ahmad wise pays great attention to the moral image of the teacher.

It requires the teacher to prioritize the interests of the younger generation. The teacher says that giving students and students a lot of knowledge will have to work hard on themselves to improve and deepen their knowledge. It can be seen from this that Ahmad Wise puts a serious demand on the profession of a teacher. He sees beautiful morals and deep erudition as the beautiful quality of the teacher.

A person who truly strives to shine light on people like the sun, to perfection, must master various professions and Sciences. From these, it can be concluded that there are problems and shortcomings that have not found a Hali solution in terms of the effectiveness of vocational guidance work, the transition of graduates to the next stage of education with their own capabilities and desires. For example, it is somehow difficult for a school vocational guidance specialist to form a positive attitude, interest and need for the choice of an independent profession in each student at the moment. From a scientific point of view, the choice of profession of an individual is due to the influence of social, economic, demographic, psychological and pedagogical factors. Today, in some general educational schools, the fact that the work of familiarizing students with the world of professions is not well established, there is no separate subject or subject for vocational guidance, no special class hours are allocated for this activity, incomplete formation of knowledge of the profession in students, educational and methodological literature, recommendations, developments, instructions, insufficient instructions and other problems indicate the relevance of this research topic. Also, a special place is occupied by the factor of influence of the family – the social condition of the family, the educational level of parents and other members of the family, the professional status of parents, the traditions and material support of the family. It is necessary to emphasize the importance of directing students to the profession through classroom and extracurricular education, and not only through the educational processes that take place in the school and the classroom. However, no detailed work has been carried out in this direction so far. It is necessary to study the state of the students in the present day, to conduct research on the definition of the profession by students of the older school age, the significant role of extracurricular and extracurricular activities in the formation of their worldview in this direction.

The problems of vocational orientation of students of secondary schools have been constantly studied in connection with vocational education, improvement, and to some extent their work has been carried out by our scientists. Many studies have been done on the issues of career choice of schoolchildren and their orientation towards the profession. H. to determine the interests and abilities of students using various questionnaire questions and tests. F. Rashidov, Sh. T. Ergashev and S. We can say the methodology for determining the professional orientation of students proposed by boltaboevs. According to this methodology, you will be asked questions about various professions and training. The questions are ordered, corresponding to the numbers on the answer sheet. Yana also served as a. Vorobyov, K. Boymirov, K. Drumov, R. Isyanov, I. Karimov, P. Mazgumov, O. Magdiyev, B. Mirzahmedov, U. Nishanaliyev, J. Ramizov, N. Shadiyev, E. The scientific work of the chorievs dealt with issues of increasing the inclination of schoolchildren to career choice and professions. Organizational pedagogical foundations of vocational guidance of schoolchildren K. Drumov, A. V. Soy, R. H. It was researched by zhurayev, V. Ye. Alexeyev, R. H. Zhurayev, A. V. Soy, H. F. Rashidov, O'. Tolipov, Sh. Khodjayevas have covered the theoretical and pedagogical aspects of muammoninmg. Sh. T. Ergashev, V. Through the integration of subjects taught in umutaim schools by Korotina, et al, the problems of forming

vocational interests in students are revealed. To the psychological problems of vocational guidance Y.M.Asadov, G.T.Yadgarova, A.Zakirov, G.S.Problems of continuity of Labor and vocational education, such as Nasriddinova, N.Muslimov and SH.Sharipov is reflected in his research. In this regard, an important place in the teachings of Eastern thinkers is occupied by the idea of providing education and training to boys and girls, teaching them a profession. The development of spiritual legacies in harmony with material values is highly skillful in the historical and literary works of many thinkers, sages, and is an eternal contribution to the world's treasure of culture.

The essence of the methodology regarding the orientation of students to the profession, as well as the conclusion and results of experimental and test work, is scientifically based. In the process of experimental work on professional orientation of adolescents, forms, methods and tools have been identified that ensure the effective course of the process of professional orientation of young people. These include:

1) form of activity-Organization of interview, questionnaire hamtsa test surveys, meeting, round table, interview, conference, seminar, debate, Ashley training, exhibition, excursion ,competition, . lecture etc;

2) methods of activity-pedagogical observation, storytelling, explanation, study of the content of sources, exhibitionism, practical training, excursion, demonstration, such methods as "mental Attack", "Red and black", "black box", "thought attack", "cluster", "decision-making technology", "ICE tear" ;

3) means of ensuring the effectiveness of activities - educational resources, auxiliary literature, pedagogical practice, samples of cultural heritage, educational and Technical Equipment, Information Technology (television, radio, computer, audio and video tape recorders), work experiences of advanced educators, etc.

So pedagogical, which is put on the professional orientation of adolescents - psychophysiological requirements led to the following conclusions in the general case:

- theoretical and practical fundamentals of professional orientation of adolescents create;
- to understand that adolescents are a complex quality of personality, manifested in their interaction with the profession chosen by their professional interest;
- hosting media shows on vocational guidance of adolescents;
- holding meetings of adolescents with cocktail veterans;
- Introduction of modern technologies to production enterprises;
- it is necessary to create recommendations and methodological guidelines for directing students to the profession. Specialists in order to help in choosing a profession tips and recommendations of (psychologists, doctors, educators, etc.) serves as one of the main factors. There are several variations of Occupational counseling. Including

FSMU technology

“You decided which profession to choose, why is there a strong interest in this profession?” highlight your thoughts using FSMU technology, through your own personal opinion (Table 1)

Table 1

FSMU technology

F	State your opinion	
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S	Show reason for your comment statement	
M	Give an example that proves the reason you showed	
U	Give an example that proves the reason you showed	

We currently have special opportunities to conduct professional orientation work in classes based on FSMU technology. This can also be seen in the example of the analysis of the path aimed at career guidance in classes.

One of the main goals of students is to make sure that labor for a person is a first necessity, a social duty, that solid and deep knowledge is needed to master any profession. Love for work and the desire to work can only be brought up in labor.

By the time of the present Wat, The Times are rapidly developing in every possible way. Accordingly, new professions are also entering us into our world. Unlike the professions known to us, the current student-youth are more interested in new professions. Chnuki's exposure to these professions is at a high level. And these professions reflect our lives in every aspect. Through new professions, we are interacting with new knowledge, new areas. Even at the request of the times, these professions are manifested in high demand rates. Including professions that require several new and day needs, such as IT professionals, freelancing, 3D programmer. Professional inclinations towards the study of this profession also indicate higher levels. No matter what profession a person chooses, having approached this profession with affection and realizing their duty and responsibility, el-u should grow into a necessary specialist-cadre who benefits the country.

Profession counseling is divided into 3 stages.

1. Preparation for the profession. This includes the process of the student until graduation from college. In this, the interest, desire of adolescents is prepared for professions taking into account their predisposition to this or that profession, information about professions is provided.

2. Finisher: when graduating from college, work is carried out towards the profession. This is to help students acquire one or another profession, depending on their ability, in the closing round. This kind of counseling goes beyond the scope of the college and is often carried out in higher education, organizations.

3. Formation of skills in the profession. This vocational work should be a finishing work, since the student works and studies in the factory and factory, as well as in the educational institutions in his area of interest. Skill generation is systematically strengthened as a result of the implementation of the plan and participation in competitions.

Professionalism. Determination of professionalism performed in 3 ways carried.

- a) on health;
- b) thoroughness of approximate preparation for the profession;
- c) psychophysiological state.

Depending on the competence of these specialists, adolescents are worthy of one profession or another

they determine that it is and give information that it is necessary to change the profession or that it is harmful to health, that its organism is not worthy of its chosen profession.

From the above, it can be seen that great allomas and thinkers looked with special attention to the socio-economic, spiritual-moral, pedagogical-psychological aspects of professional orientation, the role of the parent, school, the independent choice of the life, Labor path of the younger generation in choosing a profession. The study of the child's interest, inclinations, abilities in the direction of the craft noted the need to take into account their awareness, consistency and succession, age and individual characteristics in such a case.

- Recognition of the highest social value in the educational activities of professional education in the vocational guidance system, respect for the self-esteem of each child, teenager and young man-Girls, taking into account its social and legal freedoms;

- finding a sense of compatibility of interests , inclinations and abilities in student youth;

- special attention in the process of professional education to continuity and inclusion of children of different ages.

In place of the conclusion, it should be noted that Eastern allomas help to choose a profession in works , to study their thoughts on career orientation , to bring them into practical life, to choose a conscious profession for the growing younger generation. This is one of the main tasks of the society to educate children in the profession from an early age . They also serve the richness of understanding , imagination and knowledge inherent in the profession. Taking into account, of course, the child's abilities and interests in the direction of the younger generation to the profession will help them grow up to become a mature specialist in their profession in the future.

Testifies to the worthy contribution of our ancestors to the formation of the theory of choosing a profession. It is indisputable that the fruitful use of the rich scientific heritage of our ancestors in the process of vocational guidance in secondary schools will have a positive effect. It is one of those cases when it does not require proof that a person, by choosing the right profession, gives a huge benefit to his family, society.

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